

2035 Electrification Planning Analysis - NIGER

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Executive Summary

This study presents a least-cost electrification analysis for Niger using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Toolkit (OnSSET) tool, in alignment with national targets and the Mission 300 initiative. With only 21% of the population electrified in 2023 and significant rural-urban disparities, Niger aims to reach 80% electrification by 2035, with 85% of new connections through the national grid. Five scenarios were developed to compare technology pathways and investment implications under varying assumptions.

The results show clear trade-offs: scenarios prioritizing grid extension are generally more cost-efficient but assume ambitious annual rollout rates—up to 386,000 new grid connections per year, which far exceeds current implementation capacity. Scenarios that favor mini-grids or SHS result in higher per capita costs but may offer better feasibility in remote or conflict-prone areas.

Key limitations include outdated grid data, lack of official mini-grid geolocations, and generalized CAPEX assumptions. These constrain the accuracy of absolute investment estimates but still allow meaningful scenario comparison.

Recommendations include refining the model with updated, localized cost and infrastructure data, incorporating conflict zones in accessibility planning, and aligning OnSSET outputs with national investment plans like the PDAE and Desert to Power. Such refinements would enhance the planning relevance and implementation feasibility of electrification strategies in Niger.

1. Introduction:

The electricity sector in Niger faces major challenges: low access to electricity, weak transmission and distribution infrastructure, high costs of grid extension in remote areas, and limited deployment of off-grid and mini-grid solutions. In 2023, only 21% of the population had access to electricity, with stark disparities between urban (~70%) and rural (5–10%) areas. With electricity demand rising by around 10% annually and a low generation capacity (~317 MW in 2022), Niger has set ambitious targets: 60% electrification by 2030 and 80% by 2035.

Given its vast renewable potential, particularly solar, there is a pressing need to reach these targets affordably—especially in sparsely populated areas. This work aims to develop a least-cost electrification strategy using the optimal mix of technologies. The objective is to identify cost-effective solutions by analysing and comparing grid extension, mini-grid, and off-grid options.

This initiative also aligns with the **Mission 300** goal to provide electricity to 300 million Africans by 2030, including Niger. The country has already submitted its **Energy Compact**, detailing its strategies to achieve national electrification objectives by 2030.

These strategies aim to electrify over 2 million households via grid extension, mini-grids and off-grid solutions. Hence, for an effective achievement of these strategies, an accurate planning of electricity demand is crucial to ensure reliable supply while optimizing resource allocations. These efforts are part of the broader plan of electrification, which aligns with the Mission 300.

2. Methodology:

2.1 Study Area

This study is conducted at the national level, focusing on the Republic of Niger. The national electricity grid is divided into four (4) independent zones including the river zone (RZ, 72% of total electricity consumption), the North-Centre-East zone (NCE,

20% of total electricity consumption), the East Zone and the North zone. Figure 1 shows the study area along with the existing and planned high voltage lines, the medium voltage line as well as the electrified localities.

Figure 1: Map showing the study area along with high and medium voltages lines and current electrified locations

2.2 Data Sources

All data used for this analysis are from open-source platforms. Due to the unavailability of precise geolocated data on existing mini-grids, a key assumption was made: any settlement displaying nightlight signals and located more than 30 km from the existing national grid was considered to be served by a mini-grid.

2.3 Tools and Scenario Development

The analysis was conducted using the **OnSSET** to develop least-cost electrification scenarios for Niger. The model assumes a projected population of 39 million by 2035, with 20% residing in urban areas. Five distinct scenarios were developed:

- **Scenario 1: Grid-Priority Approach** – Aligned with national targets (85% grid, 10% off-grid, 5% mini-grid), this scenario removes constraints on annual grid

expansion (new connections or generation capacity).

- **Scenario 2: Mini-Grid Priority** – Limits the number of new grid connections per year to encourage mini-grid development.
- **Scenario 3: SHS Priority** – Emphasizes stand-alone systems by capping grid extension at 5 km and setting the mini-grid threshold to 300 households.
- **Scenario 4: Socioeconomic Growth, No Grid Constraints** – Increases electricity consumption tiers without limiting grid expansion (distance constraint set to zero).
- **Scenario 5: Socioeconomic Growth, Least-Cost Priority** – Similar to Scenario 4, but prioritizes investments based on the lowest per capita cost rather than largest settlements.

2.3.1 Consumption assumptions

Electricity consumption assumptions were defined to reflect different settlement typologies and development expectations. While the current national average consumption in Niger is approximately 310 kWh per person per year, we differentiated target demand tiers by settlement size and type. For the first three scenarios, we applied 1,200 kWh/household/year for urban areas, 365 kWh for large rural settlements, and 43 kWh for small rural settlements. In the scenario 4 and 5, we increased the target for small rural settlements by 70%, to 73 kWh/household/year, to reflect rural socioeconomic growth. These differentiated assumptions enable a more nuanced assessment of technology allocation and investment needs across various contexts.

3. Results:

Figure 2: Technology share to achieve 80% electrification rate in 2035

The figure above presents the technology mix and total investment required under five electrification scenarios to achieve 80% electricity access in Niger by 2035. Each scenario reflects a different prioritization of grid, mini-grid, and SHS solutions, and yields distinct outcomes in terms of both technology deployment and associated investment needs.

Scenario 1, aligned with government targets, strongly favors grid extension, with approximately **85%** of new connections coming from the grid. Mini-grids and SHS contribute marginally (less than 10% each). This scenario results in the **lowest investment** for these first 3 scenarios, just above **3,300 million USD**, suggesting the credibility of the government scenario.

Figure 3: Grid-Priority Scenario

In contrast, **Scenario 2**, which limits grid expansion and incentivizes mini-grid deployment, shows a more balanced technology mix: **Grid (~58%)**, **Mini-grid (~27%)**, and **SHS (~15%)**. This leads to a moderate increase in required investment, around **3,500 million USD**.

Figure 4: Mini-Grid Priority Scenario

Scenario 3 emphasizes off-grid systems, resulting in a higher share of SHS (~28%) and reduced grid and mini-grid shares. Despite fewer infrastructure needs for SHS, the **total investment increases** slightly, reflecting the high unit cost of decentralized systems in sparsely populated areas.

Figure 5: SHS Priority Scenario

Scenario 4 assumes higher electricity consumption across all areas with no constraint on grid expansion. The grid share rises again to **~85%**, while SHS and mini-grid contributions remain minimal. However, this leads to the **highest investment requirement**, exceeding **4,500 million USD**, due to increased generation and transmission costs tied to higher demand levels.

Finally, **Scenario 5** introduces a cost-optimization logic, prioritizing settlements with the lowest investment per capita. This leads to a more balanced and cost-effective technology mix (**Grid ~63%**, **SHS ~30%**) and results in a **lower investment** of around **3,400 million USD**, making it one of the most efficient scenarios from a cost perspective.

Overall, the results highlight important trade-offs between policy objectives, technology selection, and financial sustainability.

5. Discussion:

Comparing our results to national planning targets highlights **a significant gap between modelled projections and real-world feasibility**. The Plan Directeur d'Accès à l'Électricité (PDAE) aims to reach 60% electrification by 2030, and according to the 2024 Energy Compact, approximately **1,550,665 new grid connections** are still required to meet this goal. This implies a pace of about **260,000 new grid connections per year** until 2030. However, in our scenario aiming for 80% electrification by 2035, **with 85% of new connections through the grid**, as per government ambition, **an average of 386,000 new connections per year** would be required. This represents a **1.5x increase** in annual rollout pace compared to current targets, raising questions about the **practical feasibility** of such a scale-up given existing financial, technical, and institutional constraints.

Beyond rollout speed, the **accuracy of investment estimates** must also be critically assessed. While the model **reliably compares scenarios in relative terms**, the **absolute investment figures are only indicative**. Future work should focus on a **benchmarking exercise using real project data from Niger**, including procurement records, to refine cost assumptions and improve the financial realism of modeling outputs.

Another major limitation is the **lack of up-to-date data**, especially concerning infrastructure. The national grid data used dates back to **2020**, and there is **no publicly available geospatial database of existing mini-grids**. This forced the use of a strong proxy: assuming that any settlement beyond 30 km from the grid and showing nightlight emissions is served by a mini-grid. While this assumption helped compensate for the lack of data, it may lead to inaccuracies in the spatial distribution of technologies.

The study also does **not take into account the conflict and insecurity** affecting parts of Niger. These areas may be inaccessible for infrastructure deployment in the short to medium term, which **undermines the feasibility of grid or mini-grid investments**. Incorporating conflict data into future models would help prioritize electrification efforts in secure zones while exploring mobile or stand-alone solutions in high-risk areas.

In light of these limitations, **further research should aim to align least-cost electrification strategies with current national investment plans and implementation capacities**. This includes a more detailed analysis of the PDAE, the Desert to Power initiative, and donor-funded programs such as Scaling Solar and off-grid interventions supported by GIZ and USAID.

Finally, to ensure actionable insights, future modeling efforts should integrate **implementation constraints**, such as annual grid rollout capacity, funding availability, and institutional performance, as well as exploring hybrid planning approaches that combine least-cost modeling with political and logistical feasibility assessments.

6. Conclusion:

This study highlights the potential and challenges of achieving 80% electrification in Niger by 2035 using a least-cost approach. Among the five scenarios tested, grid-priority pathways offer lower total investments but rely on extremely high connection rates that may exceed practical implementation capacity. Off-grid and mini-grid options, while costlier per capita, present more flexible solutions for hard-to-reach areas.

Key insights include the critical need for updated infrastructure data, a realistic assessment of institutional and technical constraints, and a better integration of national planning instruments into scenario modeling. The limitations identified, such as assumptions on mini-grid locations, CAPEX benchmarks, and absence of conflict data, underline the importance of improving the data environment for energy planning in Niger.

Going forward, electrification strategies must balance cost-efficiency with feasibility. Integrating socio-political realities and national investment plans into future modeling will be essential to designing implementable, equitable, and resilient electrification pathways. The use of tools like OnSSET should support, not replace, practical planning aligned with on-the-ground capacity and development priorities.

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